

The role of retail trade in raising the standard of living of the rural population.

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Annotation. In this article, the reforms implemented in the spheres of production and services are an important factor in ensuring employment of the population, increasing incomes and living standards of the population. At present, the organization of seminars and training courses on information technologies and advanced trading technologies for retailers will help to solve this issue in our country.

Keywords. Trade, retail, small business, profit, income, entrepreneurship, service.

Structural changes taking place in the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, reforms carried out in the sphere of production and services are an important factor in ensuring employment of the population, increasing incomes and the quality of life of our people.

“Today, analyzing the consistent progress of our country along the path of sustainable development, we have every reason to say that decisive steps were taken last year to implement important fundamental reforms.

The main goal of these reforms is to ensure a decent level and quality of life for the population ¹. ”

Improving the level and quality of life of the population of our country is based on a more complete satisfaction of its requests and needs for material and non-material benefits. Naturally, trade occupies a special place in this important issue.

Trade is a special area that ensures the life of the population, goods produced with its participation are recognized by consumers, and the supply of goods and consumer demand are balanced. In addition, it creates real economic opportunities for trading in the return of the reproductive process.

¹ Mirziyoev Sh.M. Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rules of every leader. - T.: NMIU "Uzbekistan", 2017, 6 p.

Any production entity must ensure the sale of its products, otherwise a crisis may await it. Trade enterprises create conditions for producers to cover their costs and receive appropriate income.

Table-1

Volumes of provision of retail services to the population in Uzbekistan²

Indicators	Unit	Years		Ratio 2020 to 2019, in percent
		2019	2020	
By republic retail turnover	billion soms	188608.5	194 843.5	103.2
Population per capita	thousand soums	5582	5691.8	101.3
Turnover of retail trade in Samarkand region	billion soms	15346.6	16561.6	107.3
Population per capita	thousand soums	4011.4	4231.4	105.2

Table 1 shows that in 2020, compared to 2019, the retail trade turnover in the country increased by 3.2%, and in Samarkand region this figure increased by 7.3%. Per capita Retail trade turnover, in the study period, 1.3% in the republic, Samarkand region increased by 5.2 percent. In both cases, these indicators in the Samarkand region are slightly higher than in the republic. This situation, in our opinion, has developed under the influence of several factors. In particular, this can be explained by the relatively high incomes of the population living in the Samarkand region and the availability of goods in the retail network that can satisfy the needs of consumers.

Particular attention is paid to the final result of the socio-economic reforms being carried out in our country - an increase in the real incomes of the population by providing employment, improving their living conditions, and creating all conditions for a comfortable life.

Effective trading is a high art. This requires theoretical knowledge and practical experience from the entrepreneur. Intuition or common sense is not enough here. In the

² Trade in Uzbekistan. - T .: State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics, 2020. S. 220 and 225.

conditions of saturation of the consumer market with goods and competition, an entrepreneur who wants to maintain his importance in this area needs to have deep and comprehensive knowledge in terms of sales activities.

At present, the organization of seminars and training courses on information technology and advanced trading technologies for business entities engaged in retail trade in our country is one of the practical works to address this issue ³.

The competitive environment in the network has an impact on the constant increase in the level of knowledge of the sales staff in terms of service delivery. Competition motivates sales staff to constantly improve their knowledge. Noting that it is impossible to win the competition, it must be said that high-level specialists are required for the timely implementation of the achievements of scientific and technical developments. Failure to do so will inevitably result in the loss of the competition. It is known that the main area of competition is the market, since individual interests of free economic entities collide on it.

In 2013, the share of state retail enterprises in the retail trade turnover of our country amounted to 0.2%, and by 2016 - 0.1%. Thus, the share of state retail enterprises in the country's retail trade turnover decreased by 0.1 percent.

Table-2

Distribution of retail trade turnover by forms of ownership of economic entities in the field of trade of the Republic of Uzbekistan⁴

(at current prices, billion soums)

Years	General	Including forms of ownership		
		state	non-state	It's personal
2019	46863.0	83.8	46779.2	32842.4
2020	88071.6	111.5	87960.1	66286.2

In our opinion, it is advisable to increase the number of state-owned retailers and increase their share in the total retail turnover. Because at present, as a result of the

³ In this regard, special business seminars are held in Uzbek for sales personnel in the regions of our country. (Forta Business Education).

⁴ Trade in Uzbekistan. - T.: State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017, 26 p.

stratification of the population, there are families in need of social protection. Financial support for such families will require the opening of local shops with a limited range of goods (including children's clothing). This is consistent with the principle of a strong social policy, taking into account the demographic structure of the population of Uzbekistan.

A significant share of state-owned enterprises in the turnover of retail trade enterprises and an increase in the number of state-owned enterprises within retail trade enterprises are considered important factors in the formation of a competitive environment in the industry. We believe that this is in the interests of a wide range of consumers.

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